

Self-efficacy and Its Effect on Teachers' Job Satisfaction at University Level in Pakistan

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Abstract

This study looked at the correlation between teachers' job satisfaction at the higher education level and self-efficacy. The study was descriptive and based on correlations. The population included teachers from each of the 22 public universities in Punjab, Pakistan. A sample of 405 faculty members was selected through a two-stage sampling procedure. The data was gathered using two measures that participants self-reported. A sample size of 405 faculty members from seven public universities in the Punjab region was used to collect the data. Inferential statistical techniques were used to examine the data. The study found that self-efficacy and job satisfaction were positively correlated. Self-efficacy also affects how satisfied teachers are with their jobs. Depending on their gender and level of experience in teaching, teachers' levels of self-efficacy and job satisfaction differed substantially. In order to increase their level of contentment with working as educators, instructors ought to promote a sense of self-efficacy.

Keywords: Self-efficacy, Job Satisfaction, Higher Education

1. Introduction

The teaching profession is unique in that it only applies to teachers. According to Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2001), self-efficacy among educators is the belief that teachers are able to effectively impart knowledge to the pupils. Effectiveness in the classroom is influenced by teacher self-efficacy. Educators who believe in their own abilities are more likely to have confidence that their forthcoming endeavors will end up resulting in favorable outcomes (McLean et al., 2018). If teachers believe that they can accomplish great things, they will be more likely to achieve those great things. Similar to teacher self-efficacy, teacher job satisfaction is specific to teachers due to their unique job requirements and clients. Overall, teacher job satisfaction is an indicator of teacher commitment to the school and students, not just the profession itself

Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2001) described the self-efficacy of educators as the confidence in one's ability to teach and guide pupils successfully. Self-efficacy among teachers is a factor in their success. Teachers who are confident in their own abilities are more likely to expect positive outcomes from their efforts in the future (McLean et al., 2018). Educators who possess faith in their own skills are more likely to succeed in accomplishing their objectives. Like teacher self-efficacy, teacher work satisfaction is unique to instructors because of their particular clientele and job requirements. Overall, a teacher's level of satisfaction at work reflects not only their profession but also their dedication to the university and its students (Shaukat et al., 2019). There has not been much research on the connection between teachers' work satisfaction and their sense of self-efficacy (Infurna, 2018; Sarikaya et al., 2020). This is due to the fact that prior research on teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction focused on specific aspects of each.

A key component of success is self-efficacy. According to Lukacova et al. (2018), self-efficacy is a personality attribute that influences behavior and aids in decision-making. Self-efficacy affects a person's confidence in either a favorable or negative way. Along with confidence, self-efficacy affects someone's personality in several ways. Self-efficacy beliefs have an impact on emotions, feelings, thoughts, and actions (Guidetti et al, 2018; Ma & Cavanagh, 2018). People may act one way in one situation and completely differently in another based on their sense of self-efficacy in the context. The person's beliefs about their own self-efficacy will determine whether they will respond positively or negatively to the situation.

Personality, behavior, and attitude are all influenced by self-efficacy. Behavior is influenced by self-efficacy perception, both directly and indirectly (Mahasneh & Alwan, 2018). The level of self-efficacy a person possesses determines how they act or react in a given situation. Demirtas (2018) says that a person's level of self-efficacy will affect how they feel about a problem and what they do about it. If they have a high sense of self-efficacy, they will approach the situation constructively and with a positive attitude. Self-efficacy influences how individuals act and think. Self-efficacy does not come naturally to people. According to Stajkovic et al. (2018) that self-efficacy grows as a result of experience. The more experiences a person has, the more their self-efficacy is affected. One of the best ways to boost self-efficacy, according to Ozer and Bandura (1990), is to master skills. As they practice more, they will get better at what they do.

Individuals with high self-efficacy exhibit a range of characteristics. Those having excellent levels of self-efficacy first create objectives for themselves (Picha & Howell, 2018). The objectives serve as a framework for their work and serve

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to motivate them to improve. According to Newman et al. (2018), individuals who possess a high level of self-efficacy expend more time and effort to accomplish tasks and achieve their goals. People who have self-efficacy are happier and have greater accomplishments. On the other hand, people who lack self-efficacy do not succeed as much as people who have high levels of this quality. People with low self-efficacy are more afraid of failing and less confident in their ability to succeed (Picha & Howell, 2018). They approach a situation with the expectation that they will fail to complete the task in a satisfactory manner. People who have low levels of self-efficacy try to make up for it by constantly coming up with excuses why they cannot succeed (Stajkovic et al., 2018). Negativity can result from low self-efficacy.

Teachers' levels of satisfaction with their work are influenced by the atmosphere and culture of a school. Content teachers are essential to classroom success (Kurt & Demirbolat, 2019). Teachers tend to be happier with their jobs when they enjoy what they do. In addition, Zakariya (2000) found that teachers typically report high levels of job satisfaction in schools with fewer incidents of disruptive behavior and poor student conduct. The culture and atmosphere of the school have an effect on teacher satisfaction at work. Along with climate and culture, teacher satisfaction has an effect on retention. According to Gultekin (2019), teachers who are happy and motivated at work are more likely to stay there. Paying teachers more is one method to make them happy. According to Olsen and Huang (2019), teachers with higher wages typically experience greater levels of job satisfaction. Teacher retention is generally impacted by job satisfaction (Olsen & Huang, 2019). High levels of job satisfaction increase the likelihood that teachers will remain in their employment. Less satisfied teachers are more likely to leave their jobs. People leave miserable places quickly. Similar to how student achievement and discipline data are impacted by teacher job satisfaction. Increased student achievement will be favourably impacted by teachers who are happy in their jobs (Zakariya, 2020). Furthermore, according to Kapa and Gimbert (2018), job satisfaction levels are influenced by student behavior and adherence to guidelines. Students who behave appropriately foster a culture of learning and achievement. There is no need for teachers to be concerned about behavior obstructing education and learning.

1.1. Research Objectives

- Determine the relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction among university teachers.
- Determine the gender and teaching experience differences in self-efficacy and teachers' job university level.
- Examine the impact of self-efficacy on teachers' job satisfaction.

1.2. Research Questions

- What is relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction among university teachers?
- What are the gender and teaching experience differences in self-efficacy and teachers' job university level?
- What is the impact of self-efficacy on teachers' job satisfaction?

2. Teachers' Self-efficacy

The teaching profession is the only one where teacher self-efficacy exists. According to Ma and Cavanagh (2018), educators' self-efficacy results from their conviction that they can successfully instruct and educate pupils in addition to accomplishing their own educational objectives. Consideration is given to every facet of the teaching profession. The success of the instructor is influenced by their sense of self-efficacy. McLean et al. (2018) claim that teachers are more likely to believe that their efforts will be successful in the future if they have stronger self-efficacy beliefs. Positive accomplishments are beneficial to the field, the school, and the students as a whole. The students will benefit from the assurance of the professors. It is more likely that teachers will achieve professional success if they are confident in their abilities.

Both a teacher's success and failure are significantly influenced by their level of teacher self-efficacy. Poor student performance will result from teachers who lack self-assurance (Lukaova et al., 2018). If a teacher lacks confidence in their students' abilities or the intended learning outcomes, students will be less motivated. A teacher is more likely to fail to achieve their objectives if they lack self-assurance and belief in their abilities to succeed in the classroom and at work. Teachers' performance in the classroom will be influenced by their level of self-efficacy (Demirtas, 2018). Success as a teacher depends on having self-efficacy.

Teacher efficacy can vary from teacher to teacher when teaching a particular academic subject. Self-efficacy is subject- and context-specific for teachers (Demirtas, 2018). A teacher may have high teacher self-efficacy in the second grade but low teacher self-efficacy in the sixth grade, even if he has adequate certification for both classrooms. The perception of competence held by each teacher has an impact on the school's efficiency. How staff members feel about their own effectiveness as teachers will influence leadership decisions (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). When making decisions, university management must take into account both the individual and collective perspectives of employee self-efficacy. Teacher skills must be derived from a variety of instructional behaviors across a variety of curriculum areas in order to acquire pertinent information on teacher self-efficacy for use in leadership decisions (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001).

An accurate representation of the teaching staff's perspectives on self-efficacy cannot be obtained from a single data survey. The data collected on teacher self-efficacy will serve as the foundation for the institution's leadership decisions. Teachers' levels of self-efficacy vary depending on the educational setting. One aspect of teaching is the use of teacher self-efficacy perspectives in classroom management. Wilson et al. (2018) say that the belief that a teacher is capable of setting up and managing a secure classroom is the concept of teacher self-efficacy beliefs in classroom management. Teachers must be able to manage their classrooms effectively. It takes time and effort to comprehend the fundamentals of classroom management. A safe and well-managed classroom setting supports children's overall academic success. Teacher efficacy includes instructional strategies as well as classroom management, which is one aspect of teacher self-efficacy. According to Tschannen-Moran and Hoy's (2001) findings, teachers who were confident in their own abilities to employ instructional strategies were better able to plan and carry out activities and courses that enhanced student learning (Wilson et al., 2018). Guidance seems to vary depending on the needs of the students and the curriculum areas. A high quality of instruction will boost student achievement and subject-matter mastery if the teacher has strong self-efficacy beliefs (McLean et al., 2018; Sensoy & Yildirim, 2018). The teacher's and the students' successful outcomes will contribute to their increased self-efficacy. More successes will inspire both the teacher and the student to continue in the right direction. More success for the student will motivate both the teacher and the pupil to continue in the right direction. The quality of a teacher's instruction will improve student achievement and subject-matter mastery if the teacher has strong self-efficacy beliefs (McLean et al., 2018; Sensoy & Yildirim, 2018). The positive outcomes will make both the teacher and the students feel more capable. Both the teacher and the student will be motivated to move forward in the right direction if there are additional successes. Both the teacher and the student will be motivated to proceed appropriately if the student continues to succeed. Wilson et al. (2018) say that educators who are confident in their ability to ensure that every student is motivated to learn are those who have high levels of self-efficacy in this area. Student achievement rises because students are more likely to comprehend and absorb information when they are engaged.

3. Teachers' Job Satisfaction

It is essential for all employees to have a job they enjoy. It is difficult to define the concept of "job satisfaction" (Ford et al., 2018; Gultekin, 2019). Because every employee's level of job satisfaction may vary, it is confusing. Despite being difficult to define and quantify, job satisfaction is an essential concept for all employees (Yavuz, 2018). The most common and accepted definition of job satisfaction is a person's level of contentment or discontent with their employment situation (Gultekin, 2019). Employees who are happy and will help the organization succeed are sought after by employers.

People's feelings regarding their work are referred to as job satisfaction. There is no evidence of job satisfaction (Gultekin, 2019). One cannot tell from looking at someone's face whether they are satisfied or not. Job satisfaction can be difficult to evaluate or quantify because it is a subjective feeling. Due to the fact that job satisfaction is an internal sense about one's work or job, it is typically not apparent. Positivity regarding work can include feelings of job satisfaction. In comparison to those who detest their work, people who love their employment are more successful and are more inclined to take on additional responsibilities (Dogan et al., 2018). Additionally, increased productivity is a direct result of increased job satisfaction. People who are happier and healthier at work are more satisfied at their jobs (Kurt & Demirbolat, 2019).

Capri and Guler (2018) assert that teaching is a stressful occupation. Overall, teacher job satisfaction reflects not only the profession but also the teacher's dedication to the school and students (Shaukat et al., 2019). A variety of special projects have an impact on teacher job satisfaction. Different aspects of education are essential for certain individuals. According to Gultekin (2019), there are a variety of factors that influence how satisfied teachers are with their work as a whole.

For instance, some educators place a high value on peer cooperation. If a teacher works in a small school with few other teachers, he or she may not have the opportunity to collaborate. The lack of collaboration will result in teachers' low levels of job satisfaction. The same teacher will have high levels of job satisfaction if he works in a school that places an emphasis on cooperation because of the opportunities for collaboration and engagement (Granziera & Perera, 2019). Teachers place a high value on various aspects of the profession. Teachers who are content in their positions will be more beneficial to their schools. Teachers' high levels of job satisfaction will lead to schools' success and higher academic standards (Dogan et al., 2018). Job satisfaction is essential for increasing student achievement (Luleci & Coruk, 2018). Teachers are more likely to care and work harder when they are in a place they enjoy. When teachers are satisfied with their work, they are happier and have better relationships with students and other staff members (Yavuz, 2018). On the other hand, instructors who are dissatisfied with their work may be detrimental to the institution. Teachers feel bad about their school when they are unhappy in their job (Dogan et al., 2018). The hostile attitudes will be detrimental to the school. Students and educators will be unable to foster learning and achievement due to the negative emotions. Teacher job satisfaction is very important to both students' success and the success of schools.

4. Self-efficacy and Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Recently, there has been a greater interest in teacher self-efficacy and work satisfaction due to increased demand on universities to perform (Granziera & Perera, 2019). There are several facets to teacher work satisfaction, teacher self-efficacy, and teaching in general. For instance, participation in the teaching and learning process promotes teachers' job satisfaction and self-efficacy (Granziera & Perera, 2019). Student achievement is influenced by teachers' job satisfaction and sense of competence. Additionally, it has been discovered that teacher job satisfaction and self-efficacy are crucial for retention, instruction quality, and student learning outcomes (Zakariya, 2020). The condition of the schools can be improved through increased teacher work satisfaction and self-efficacy. Meaningful findings were obtained from examining teacher self-efficacy and work happiness in the same study. The study conducted by Caprara et al. in 2003 aimed to generalize the concepts of work satisfaction and teacher self-efficacy. They came to the conclusion that teacher self-efficacy affects satisfaction at work.

Importantly, Caprara et al. (2006) investigated whether teacher job satisfaction and student academic progress are influenced by teacher self-efficacy perspectives. How well instructors can perform fundamental teaching activities and job functions depends on their level of self-efficacy and job happiness. Self-efficacy beliefs in teachers have a favorable impact on both their job happiness and students' academic success. A more supportive environment for the teachers and children can be produced if school administrators concentrate more on teacher self-efficacy. Positive teacher self-efficacy also lays a basis for skill confidence, which fosters drive to perform well.

The connection between educator characters attributes and instructor self-efficacy and occupation fulfillment was concentrated by Perera et al. (2018) with 574 Australian instructors. The most significant levels of educator self-adequacy and occupation fulfillment were found in instructors who scored in the composed (most elevated) bunch on the character profile. These teachers showed greater interest in both work-related activities and educational activities. Some educators who participated heavily in educational activities reported lower levels of job satisfaction. This might have happened as a result of being overburdened with academic obligations. In addition, the research that was carried out by Ramos et al. (2018), the researchers came to the conclusion that teacher job satisfaction is linked to life satisfaction and positive affect. The fact that teacher self-efficacy is linked to collective self-efficacy is a surprising finding from the research; However, there is no correlation between teacher job satisfaction and collective self-efficacy. Positive working conditions are necessary for teachers to be satisfied in their positions.

With a sample of 536 Croatian high school teachers, Buri and Moe (2020) investigated how teachers' passion is influenced by their job satisfaction and sense of self-efficacy. As indicated by the discoveries, educators' excitement is emphatically impacted by self-adequacy and occupation fulfillment. At the point when the educator's degrees of occupation fulfillment and self-adequacy were higher, they were more excited. Instructors who lacked self-efficacy and job satisfaction would also be less enthusiastic. Teachers' levels of self-efficacy and job satisfaction can rise in a supportive setting (Zakariya, 2020). Within their schools, school leaders have a lot to think about and do for the staff, which makes up a large portion. According to Caprara et al. (2003) that teacher job satisfaction and self-efficacy beliefs are essential in the school setting and may serve as a tool for school management and success. The higher a person's level of self-confidence, the greater their likelihood of success and job satisfaction.

5. Research Methodology

5.1. Research Design

The association between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of faculty members at universities was examined using a descriptive correlational research design. This study sought to establish a relationship between the self-efficacy and level of job satisfaction of university professors.

5.2. Population, Sample and Sampling

The data were collected using a survey method. All academic staff members at Punjab's public universities were included in the population. In Punjab, there were 13 general public universities. The sample used in the research included all respondents drawn at random from the population (Muhammad et al., 2023; Siddique et al., 2021; Siddique et al., 2023). A two-stage sampling at random procedure was adopted. At first, 50 percent of the public institutions were picked from a list of thirteen. In this way, seven public universities were chosen. There are a total of 5050 teachers employed by public universities. 505 university teachers from the first phase were selected at random for the second phase. Frankle and Wallen (2012) suggested that the sample size might be more important in research studies. A final sample of 400 or more may be obtained in terms of time and resources if the population exceeds 5,000 (Gay et al., 2011). While other methods of correspondence, such as online communication, were utilized to collect data from other universities, the researcher personally visited universities in Lahore. The instruments had a response rate of 80% (n = 405).

5.3. Research Instruments

Survey research and a correlational design were used in this study. The data came from seven public universities in the Punjab region, with a sample size of 405 university teachers. Two instruments were adapted. Firstly, the "Teacher Self-

efficacy Scale” was utilized to measure teacher self-efficacy (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). The Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) developed by Spector (1994), which consists of 36 items, was used to measure teacher job satisfaction. Both scales had a reliability level of 0.81.

6. Results

Table 1: Correlation between Self-efficacy and Job Satisfaction

Variables	<i>n</i>	<i>r</i> -value	<i>Sig.</i>
Self-efficacy and Job Satisfaction	405	.845**	.000

** $p < .001$ (2-tailed)

Table 1 portrayed the association between job satisfaction and self-efficacy. Self-efficacy was found to strongly correlate with teachers’ job satisfaction ($r = .845^{**}$, $n = 405$, $p.001$).

Table 2: Gender Wise Comparison in Self-efficacy and Job Satisfaction

Variables	Gender	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>P</i>
Self-efficacy	Male	218	139.1239	17.97203	3.485	375.385	.007
	Female	187	132.4439	20.24874			
Job Satisfaction	Male	218	71.7385	9.96263	3.002	372.501	.000
	Female	187	68.5187	11.40003			

An “independent sample t-test” was employed in Table 2 to compare self-efficacy and job satisfaction mean scores by gender. At $p = .05$. It was shown that self-efficacy and work satisfaction differed significantly.

Table 3: One-way ANOVA on Self-efficacy and Job Satisfaction based on Teaching Experience

Variables	Sum of Squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Self-efficacy Error	4883.98	5	976.79	2.67	.022
	145959.38	399	365.81		
Job Satisfaction Error	150843.36	404		3.39	.005
	1907.51	5	381.50		
	44846.79	399	112.39		
	46754.31	404			

The results of a one-way analysis of variance on the number of years in experience in teaching were shown in Table 3. According to the findings, teachers’ teaching experiences significantly influenced self-efficacy and job satisfaction.

Table 4: Effect of Self-efficacy on Job Satisfaction

Variables	<i>B</i>	<i>t</i> -value	<i>Sig.</i>	Model <i>R</i> Square
Self-efficacy & Job Satisfaction	.845	31.69	.001	.714

Table 4 revealed the findings of the linear regression, where the R^2 value of the predictor, which was .714, explained the variation in the criteria. Self-efficacy therefore explains the variation in teacher work satisfaction (71.4%). The beta value of .845 is significant at $p = .001$. The results demonstrated that self-efficacy had a substantial impact on work satisfaction, with a value of .845 and a p -value of .001.

7. Discussion

The current study looked into the connection between self-efficacy and university-level job satisfaction. McLean et al. claim that (2018), teachers are more likely to believe that their efforts will result in improved student achievement and

results if they have stronger self-efficacy beliefs. Additionally, according to Lukaova et al. (2018), teachers who are more self-assured will have a favorable effect on their students. Teachers with high levels of job satisfaction will make more positive contributions to their school, just like teachers with high levels of teacher self-efficacy. Dogan et al. (2018) stated that a high level of job satisfaction among teachers will lead to success and improve school academic quality. According to Luleci and Coruk (2018), job satisfaction is an essential factor in elevating student achievement. According to Yavuz (2018), teachers are happier and have more positive interactions with students and other staff members when their job satisfaction rises.

Students' success is directly correlated with job satisfaction among teachers. In addition, there has been an increase in interest in teacher job satisfaction and self-efficacy in recent years as a result of increased demands on schools to perform (Granziera & Perera, 2019). In addition, teacher job satisfaction and self-efficacy have been found to have a significant impact on teacher retention, instruction quality, and student learning outcomes (Zakariya, 2020). Self-efficacy and job satisfaction among teachers can both improve student achievement and overall university success. The current study may add to the body of knowledge regarding the level of job satisfaction experienced by university professors because it focuses on the most prominent issues that arise within the university setting. In this day and age of enormous social change, competition for university professors, engagement, and retention, teaching self-efficacy is the key to determining teacher well-being and job satisfaction.

8. Conclusion

This study sought to investigate the relationship between self-efficacy and work satisfaction. The results show a significant relationship between self-efficacy and work satisfaction. According to the study, self-efficacy and work satisfaction were also shown to be influenced by gender and experience. Male instructors had better levels of work satisfaction and self-efficacy than other males in the teaching profession. Using the method of regression analysis, self-efficacy and work satisfaction were also investigated. The results showed that self-efficacy had a substantial impact on satisfaction with job.

8.1. Practical implications

There are several practical ramifications for the field of higher education as a result of the teacher self-efficacy's ability to predict teachers' job satisfaction. This study validated that among university professors, teacher self-efficacy is a predictor of job happiness. This information can help university leadership by demonstrating how teachers' work happiness and self-efficacy affect students' achievement. According to research, teacher job satisfaction and self-efficacy are extremely important for retention, instruction quality, and student learning outcomes (Zakariya, 2020). The condition of the university can be improved through increased teacher job satisfaction and self-efficacy. How well instructors can perform fundamental teaching activities and job functions depends on their level of self-efficacy and satisfaction with their work. Self-efficacy beliefs in teachers have a favorable impact on both their job happiness and students' academic success. A more hospitable environment for the professors and students is produced if university administrators can concentrate more on teacher self-efficacy (Caprara et al., 2006). Managers of universities must prioritize teacher retention. Because they are dissatisfied, teachers quit their jobs (Carver-Thomas & Darling-Hammond, 2017).

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